

SANSA NEWSLETTER

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WHY SPECIES IDENTIFICATIONS ARE STILL A PROBLEM

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Almost a third (739 spp.) of South African species were described from 1900–1920 focusing largely on the fauna of the coastal provinces, as most arachnologists were stationed there. From 1960 to 1980, there was a considerable decline in the description of new species due to a lack of practicing taxonomists. However, during the last three decades, there has been a resurgence; more than 700 species have been described since 1980, mainly due to new appointments, modern taxonomic revisions, the training of several South African taxonomists, and the efforts of taxonomists overseas.

Unfortunately, the original descriptions of many species described from 1700–1950 are often rudimentary, known only from one sex, lacking detailed morphological data and drawings or detailed collecting data. Most of the type specimens are also housed in overseas museums and are not easily obtainable for research or are lost. Most of the older descriptions were based on specimens stored in alcohol in museum collections and unfortunately, many specimens lose their colour in alcohol. This resulted in many of the described species lacking descriptions of life colour.

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Presently 2300 species are known from South Africa and the following is known about them:

- 1325 spp. are endemic to South Africa (58.5%)
- 126 spp. (5.6%) are Threatened and of Special Concern
- 693 spp. (30.6%) are Data Deficient (DD)
- 1444 spp. (63.8%) are widely distributed with no known threats and are of Least Concern (LC)
- >230 spp. are recognized as new and needs to be described

The following problems around the Data Deficient species have been identified:

- 36 spp. were described without exact locality data in South Africa
- 946 spp. are known from only one sex
- 23 spp. were described from juveniles

The species of Special Concern need monitoring to evaluate threats and the species listed as Rare need additional collecting to determine the distribution range.

Through the SANSA newsletter we are trying to address some of these problems by publishing informative papers.

- New data (63 spp.)
- First records for South Africa (21 spp.)
- Description of the opposite sex (2 spp.)
- Observations on species behaviour (39 spp.)
- Checklists of survey projects (19 articles)
- Photo identification guides (70 volumes)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

All the new information on South African species would not have been possible without the contributions made by all the **photographers** that make their photographs available to SANSA.

NEW PUBLICATIONS

LOGGHE G. & JOCQUÉ R. 2023. A new species of *Hermippus* Simon, 1893 from Tanzania and the description of the male of *H. septemguttatus* Lawrence, 1942 (Araneae, Zodariidae). *Journal of the Belgian Arachnological Society* 38(2): 91–115.

ABSTRACT: Both sexes of *Hermippus valentinus* sp. nov. are described based on material from the Tanga Region in north-eastern Tanzania. The unknown male of *Hermippus septemguttatus* Lawrence, 1942 is described on specimens from coastal localities in Mozambique. A key to the Afrotropical species of *Hermippus* Simon, 1893 is provided.

Notes on the male of *Hermippus septemguttatus*

The male of *Hermippus septemguttatus*, which was previously known only from a female specimens from KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa, is described in this paper based on new material from coastal localities in Mozambique.

Male measurements: total length 6.64, carapace length 3.64, width 2.88, height 2.12. Colour (Fig. 1): carapace and chelicerae uniform reddish brown; chillum, labium and endites lighter reddish brown; sternum orange; legs yellow, metatarsus and tarsus darker. Abdomen: dorsum black with seven white spots (Fig. 2): one in front, two on either side and two in front of spinnerets (one small and one large), sides with irregular white markings, venter pale brown to nearly white with several irregular brown and black markings; spinnerets pale brown. *Variation:* carapace nearly black in some specimens; darker markings on dorsum differ in size and shape but clearly present in all studied specimens; venter sometimes uniform pale brown without darker spots.

The distribution of *H. septemguttatus* is remarkable as it appears to be the only zodariid with a strictly coastal distribution occurring only in forest along the sea, including mangroves.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (from SANSa database):

KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hellsgate/Ndlozi Military Base (-28.011, 32.444); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St. Lucia (-28.36, 32.41); Nyalazi plantation, St Lucia (-28.243, 32.390); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56).

Map showing distribution of *Hermippus septemguttatus*

Figures 1–2. *Hermippus septemguttatus*. 1. Male. 2. Female. After Logghe & Jocqué (2023).

A STRANGE NON-AFRICAN SPIDER

Two new spider genera, *Rhincosmetus* and *Rhinoliparus* belonging to the family Theridiidae were recently described. They share the presence in males of a clypeus protrusion of which the frontal top is provided with specialized bent setae, with swollen and recurved tip, call cotyledonoid setae.

VANUYTVEN H., JOCQUÉ R. & DEELEMAN-REINHOLD C. 2024. Two new theridiid genera from Southeast Asia (Araneae: Theridiidae, Argyrodinae): males with a nose for courtship. *Journal of the Belgian Arachnological Society* 39 (1), supplement: 1–96.

THE TABLE MOUNTAIN NATIONAL PARK

HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR- SCHOEMAN A.S. 2024. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Table Mountain National Park in the Western Cape Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 66(1), a1797. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v66i1.1797>

Photo: Nicole Dippenaar

ABSTRACT: The Table Mountain National Park (TMNP) is an iconic protected area in South Africa, renowned for the high levels of plant and animal species richness and endemism. An annotated species list of spiders presently known from the TMNP is provided. The checklist was compiled from data collected from the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) database. A total of 261 species from 50 families and 167 genera are presently protected in the park. The most species-rich families are the Salticidae (31 spp.), Thomisidae (26 spp.) and Araneidae (20 spp.), while 13 families are represented by singletons. The global distribution, endemism and IUCN Red List status of each species is provided.

Conservation implications: Seventy-seven per cent of the species have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern (200 spp.), while 31 species are Data Deficient, four species were not evaluated, and 26 species of special concern are identified. Of these, 13 spp. are Rare, three each are Critically Rare and Endangered, six are Vulnerable and one is near threatened. The TMNP protects approximately 11.4% of the total South African spider fauna and it is the type locality for 31 species. Although the TMNP and Cape Peninsula more broadly is a hotspot of endemic species for various plant and animal taxa: a proportionally small proportion of the spider species are of significant conservation concern.

Keywords: conservation; endemism; Fynbos Biome; South African National Survey of Arachnida.

Figures 1–2. Theridiosomatidae species from the Table Mountain National Park. 1. Female. 2. Male. Photos: Peter Webb.

Figures 3–5. Species from the Table Mountain National Park. 3. *Ubacisi capensis* male (Cyatholipidae). 4. *Vidole capensis* (Phyxelididae). 5. *Spermophora peninsulae*. Photos: Jan Bosselaers.

Amethyst sunbird feeding golden-orb web spider to chicks

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Stephan van Wyk of Storm Hollow Forest Retreat, near Plettenberg Bay, invited a few birders to a walk at his lodge. It has a varied habitat with coastal forest, fynbos, and grassland. Above his garage was an amethyst sunbird's nest containing two chicks.

Over the next two days, I photographed the female feeding her chicks - most of her victims were spiders. One time, she arrived at the nest with a big golden orb spider and immediately rammed it down the chicks gaping throat (Figs 4, 5). A more revolting mouthful is hard to imagine. Most of the body seemed to be inside its throat, but long, black, jointed, hairy legs, stuck out of one side of its mouth and a small section of yellow and black abdomen stuck out the other. Her method of getting it all down was to thrust it deeper and deeper down the chicks throat; how it didn't gag, I do not know. Finally, the sunbird's bill, and its a long bill, and some of its head was in the chicks throat and the spider was gone.

I have seen a rattling cisticola, a similar sized bird, securely caught in a golden orb spider's web, similar to the web in Fig. 1. So, how the sunbird was able to catch the spider is a mystery. Possibly, it hovers in front of the web, seizes the spider with that long bill and flying backwards, reverses out safely.

Sometimes, after she had fed a chick, it turned upside down and presented its cloaca; then using the tip of her multi-use, curved bill; she reached in and plucked out a faecal sac (Fig. 6) - flew away and dropped it. It was mind-boggling that a formidable looking, golden orb spider can be swallowed, digested and later emerge, neatly packaged in a small, cream coloured faecal sac. The spider was identified by the hairy brush on its jointed legs as one of the golden orb spiders, *Trichonephila fenestrata* (Fig. 1).

Figures 4 & 5. Amethyst sunbird female feeding the chicks a golden orb-web spider. Photo: Ian Thomas.

Figure 6. Female with faecal sac plucked from a chick. Photo: Ian Thomas.

Figures 1a & b. Golden orb-web *Trichonephila fenestrata* female. Photo: Stephan van Wyk.

Figure 2. Amethyst sunbird immature male. Photo: Patrick Raymond.

Figure 3. Amethyst sunbird female. Photo: Patrick Raymond.

EFFECT OF WEATHER ON THE WEBS OF *ARGIOPE AUSTRALIS*

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The photographs (Figs 1–8) were taken on a misty morning at Mpetsane Conservation Estate, in the Free State. This was after some bad weather with patches of frost in the mornings, some very strong wind, and a storm with 60 mm of rain. The webs differ from the typical *Argiope* webs (Figs 9 & 10) in having distinct variations in the width of the free zone (see arrow Fig. 2) being very

wide (Figs 2–8) compared to the typical narrow zone (Figs 9 & 10) made in the summer during warm days (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones, 2021).

REFERENCE: DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & JONES A. 2022. More on the garden orb-web spider *Argiope australis* (Walckenaer, 1805) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 40: 19–22.

Important differences between *Poltys* and *Cyphalonotus* (Araneae: Araneidae)

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Recent studies define *Cyphalonotus* as a genus that resembles *Poltys*, but they differ in eye arrangement, legs, genital details and size ratio between the sexes (Yu K *et al.*, 2022). Both genera sit with the legs tightly drawn close to the body. They are both nocturnal orb-web dwellers and in both genera the webs are finely meshed orbs (Fig. 12).

The genus *Poltys* C.L. Koch, 1843 is represented by 43 species of which nine are known from Africa and only one *Poltys furcifer* Simon, 1881 is reported from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2024). *Poltys* can be recognized by several characters (Smith, 2005, 2006; Hawes, 2020).

- Carapace pear-shaped.
- Anterior eyes on an eye tubercle (Figs 3, 4) and the posterior lateral eyes are widely separated from other eyes (Fig. 3).
- Abdomen often with humps and tubercles and smooth and roughly haired patches often with small sclerotized plates (Figs 1, 2).
- Epigyne without a scape (Fig. 5).

The genus *Cyphalonotus* Simon, 1895 is represented by eight species with three species from the Afrotropical Region and one *Cyphalonotus larvatus* (Simon, 1881) from South Africa. It can be recognized by several characters (Archer 1965; Yu K *et al.*, 2022).

- Carapace pear-shaped.
- Anterior eyes on an eye tubercle (Figs 7–9) and the posterior lateral eyes closer to the other eyes (Fig. 8).
- Abdomen often with humps and tubercles and smooth and roughly haired patches (Figs 6, 7).
- Epigyne with long scape (Fig. 10).

Both genera are nocturnally active, and build finely meshed orb-webs (Figs 11–12). The spiders are cryptically camouflaged and during the day they hide motionless on vegetation with the legs drawn tightly around the prosoma and just the median eyes, which are situated on the anterior of the eye tubercle, protruding between the legs. In this position they often resemble part of a dead twig, a gall or a broken piece of wood.

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YU K, KUNTNER M. & CHENG R. 2022. Phylogenetic evidence for an independent origin of extreme sexual size dimorphism in a genus of araneid spiders (Araneae: Araneidae). *Invertebrate Systematics* 36(1): 48–62. doi:10.1071/IS21019

POLTYS

Figures 1–4. *Poltys furcifer*. 1–2. Females. 3. Eye pattern lateral view. 4. Eye pattern, dorsal view. 5. Epigyne. Credits: 1. Ian Ridell. 2. Julie Coetzee. 3–4. After Yu K *et al.* (2022). 5. Hawes (2020).

CYPHALONOTUS

Figures 6–12. *Cyphalonotus larvatus*. 6. Females anterior view. 7. Female lateral view. 8. Eye pattern lateral view. 9. Dorsal view. 10. Epigyne. 11–12. Female in dense orb-webs. Credits: 6, 7, 11, 12. Peter Webb. 8. After Yu K *et al.* (2022). 9. Charles Haddad. 10. Archer (1965).

NEW PUBLICATIONS FROM SOUTHERN AFRICA

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2024. Quick keys to the Bominae genera of South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 49: 15–20. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10878262>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., BIRD T.L. & WEBB P. 2024. Abdominal colour patterns of the sand diving spider *Ammoxenus amphalodes* (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) from South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 49: 12–14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10878622>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2024. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the South African Cape Floristic Kingdom. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 79 (1): 1–22 [see *SANSA Newsletter* 49: 8] <https://doi.org/10.1080/0035919X.2024.2324912>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A., LOTZ L. & WIESE L. 2024. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Garden Route National Park. *SANSA Newsletter* 49: 23–33. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10878474>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2024. Records of *Artema atlanta* Walckenaer, 1837 from South Africa (Araneae: Pholcidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 49: 21–22. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10877874>

HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2024. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Table Mountain National Park in the Western Cape Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 66(1), a1797. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v66i1.1797>

LOGGHE G. & JOCQUÉ R. 2023. A new species of *Hermippus* Simon, 1893 from Tanzania and the description of the male of *H. septemguttatus* Lawrence, 1942 (Araneae, Zodariidae). *Journal of the Belgian Arachnological Society* 38(2): 91–115.

MUNYAI T.C. & SCHOEMAN C., 2024. A tribute to Professor Stefan H. Foord. *Koedoe* 66(1), a1813. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v66i1.1813>

THE WONDER WORLD OF SPIDERS

SMALL SPIDERS MAKE LARGE WEBS

Allen Jones observed numerous small orb-webs of immature spiders in the field at Mpetsane in the Free State during April-May. What is so amazing is that such a small spider (1.5 mm) is able to produce enough silk to daily build a web of 40 mm diameter.

Some more small spiders (*Cyrtophora citricola*) with large webs photographed at Mpetsane by Allen Jones.

ARACHNID PREY OF THE FISCAL SHRIKE *LANIUS COLLARIS*

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Members of the genus *Lanius* display predatory behaviour like that of raptors. The fiscal shrike, (*Lanius collaris*), also known as Jan Fiskaal, fiskaallaksman or "Jackie Hanger" is a common species that occurs throughout South Africa (Figs 1 & 2). They have a varied diet, consisting mainly of invertebrates, but a wide variety of small frogs, small snakes, lizards, crickets, bugs, beetles, and even other birds (e.g. Red-billed Quelea) are also preyed on (Soobramoney & Downs, 2004). Because a large proportion of spiders are small, little is known about them being prey of the fiscal shrike (Soobramoney & Downs, 2004). The first report on a shrike feeding on an *Argiope australis* spider was by Jones (2009) when he discovered the spider impaled on a barbed wire in the Free State.

The birds have three main foraging methods: 1. ground foraging, 2. air foraging, and 3. surface gleaning (Harris & Arnott, 1988). They sometimes catch larger prey but they do not possess strong talons for handling these large prey. However they have overcome this limitation by impaling large prey, using sharp objects, such as barbed wire, cacti, thorns and yucca plants to impale their prey (Beven & England, 1969). Impaling help to kill and overpower large prey otherwise still alive and to store the extra food.

Three arachnid species were observed impaled on barbed wire at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE), situated in the Eastern Free State highlands. In the absence of thorn trees in the Free State, barbed wire is possibly the best object to use to impale prey.

The prey was identified as a baboon spider *Harpactira hamiltoni* (Theraphosidae) (Figs 3–4) a ground dweller commonly found at MCE. The second one was a web dweller *Argiope australis* of the family Araneidae (Figs 5–6). The species are found daily in their orb-webs made between grass (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones, 2021). The third is a member of the Solifugae (Figs 7–9). They are active ground dwellers, and it was the first record of a solifugid being preyed on by a Fiscal Shrike.

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Figures 1–2. The fiscal shrike, *Lanius collaris*. Photos: Allen Jones.

Figures 3–4. *Harpactira hamiltoni* (Theraphosidae). Photos: Allen Jones.

Figures 5–6. *Argiope australis* (Araneidae). Photos: Allen Jones.

Figures 7–9. *Solpugema* sp. (Solpugidae). Photos: Allen Jones.

OBSERVATION ON THREE FLOWER CRAB SPIDERS (ARANEAE: THOMISIDAE: *THOMISUS*) FROM SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT: The general behaviour of three crab spider species *Thomisus citrinellus* Simon, 1875, *T. daradioides* Simon, 1890 and *T. stenningi* Pocock, 1900 are discussed. They are common flower dwellers found in gardens. With their strong front legs, prey are grabbed, and overpowered by their strong venom enabling them to kill prey that are frequently 2-4 times their size. They prey on seven insect orders and flies were the most commonly caught prey followed by bees. Most of the prey (79%) are caught in the neck region. They can change colour but only 53% of the spider were found on flowers of the same colour.

Keywords: feeding behaviour, biodiversity, colour change, mating, South African National Survey of Arachnida, *Thomisus citrinellus*, *Thomisus stenningi*, *Thomisus daradioides*.

INTRODUCTION

Spiders represent one of the most common predator groups found in ecosystems and are specially adapted to a predatory way of life. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) spiders were widely sampled including large numbers of Thomisidae. Presently 144 thomisid species are known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). They are commonly sampled from vegetation but also play an important role in agroecosystems (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

Thomisus is known from more than 100 species (World Spider Catalog, 2024) with 42 species recorded from the Afrotropical Region and 16 from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). *Thomisus* species have characteristic adaptations that allow a very efficient life on plants. They have lost the ability to move about swiftly and spend their entire lives on plants, usually in and on flowers (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

Thomisus species are active during the day and commonly found on flowering plants and they are frequently photographed. As part of SANSA, an online virtual museum was operational (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012), and more than 9000 images of spiders have been received from the public throughout the country over ten years.

We were able to identify three South African common *Thomisus* species: *Thomisus citrinellus* Simon, 1875, *T. daradioides* Simon, 1890 and *T. stenningi* Pocock, 1900 from photographs taken in the field with prey. The prey species, bite sites, position on the flowers and the level of colour-matching with the flower were noted as well as notes on their mating and egg laying behaviour.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 300 photographs taken in the field of *Thomisus* spp. feeding by 26 photographers were examined. In 141 of these photographs the spider and prey could be identified. Since crab spiders do not chew their prey, the outer skin of the prey stays intact, which allows identification.

Figure 1. *Thomisus stenningi* female feeding on a fly with two males fighting on her abdomen. Photo: Martie Rheeder.

Figure 2. *Thomisus daradioides* female feeding on a fly, with the small brown male on her abdomen waiting to mate. Photo: Martie Rheeder.

Figure 3. *Thomisus citrinellus* female and male busy mating. The dark legs of the male could be seen grabbing her abdomen from below. Photo: Martie Rheeder.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

THOMISUS MORPHOLOGY

The *Thomisus* females (7–12 mm) have strong bodies, good eyesight, and well-developed tactile sense organs. They are crab-like in appearance (Figs 1–3). Their strong front legs bear rows of strong spines and enable them to grab prey from the air (Fig. 4). The females have cryptic colouration and at least to the human eye, often matches the colour of the flower where they wait for prey.

Camouflage is a powerful and widespread way of avoiding detection or recognition. The females can change colour to blend in with the flowers they occupy and they frequently shift from flower to flower for better opportunities to hunt. They sometimes spend several days on only one flower, which then allow them to change colour effectively to blend in with the surroundings. The new colour is displayed uniformly across the head, legs, and abdomen. Cryptic colouration is assumed to be beneficial to predators as they are not seen by the prey. But with the spiders taking up position on the flower during the day with their front legs spread widely (Fig. 4) it also protect them against predators such as birds.

The males (2-4 mm) are much smaller than the females (Fig. 2) Marked sexual dimorphism is also found in shape and colour. The small male mature before the female, stop feeding and then spend all their time searching for females.

Mating: Females and males make little use of sight during the mating process. When the male encounters a female of the same species, he climbs onto her abdomen where he stay until she is ready to mate (Fig. 2). He is agile and moves to her venter to mate (Fig. 3). The shortness of the palpal appendage and the embolus makes it impossible for him to reach the epigyne from above. The female frequently feeds during the mating process.

The males outnumber females. A females are frequently found with one to two suitors gathered around her waiting for her to mature (Fig. 1). The males often get into fights that result in the loss of limbs and sometimes death. Only two photographs showed females feeding on males (Fig. 5).

Egg sac: The egg sac is usually deposited in folded leaves or other plant material (Fig. 6). The female defends the egg sac until the spiderlings emerge and start to disperse.

Figure 4–6. *Thomisus* spp. 4. Yellow *Thomisus stenningi* females waiting for prey. 5. *Thomisus daradioides* female feeding on a male. 6. *Thomisus* female on her egg sac deposited between flowers. Photos: 4. Peter Webb. 5. Allen Jones. 6. Martie Rheeder.

THOMISUS SPECIES INVOLVED

Only females photographed in the field on flowers with prey in their chelicerae were evaluated. In total seven species were identified, but 84% of the species belong mainly to three species that are very commonly found in South Africa: *T. citrinellus* (29%) (Fig. 7A), *T. daradioides* (25%) (Fig. 8A) and *T. stenningi* (30%) (Fig. 9A).

THOMISUS CITRINELLUS

Figures 7 (A–C). A. *Thomisus citrinellus* female and male. B. Male palp. C. Epigyne. Credits: A. Peter Webb. B & C. After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983).

PREY SPECIES

The three *Thomisus* species catch prey mainly from the following insect orders: Diptera (flies), Hymenoptera (bees and wasps), Lepidoptera (moths & butterflies), Orthoptera (crickets & grasshoppers), Thysanoptera (thrips) and Coleoptera (beetles). Flies were the most commonly caught prey, comprising just less than half of the total number at 42%. They are followed by the bees at 32%, with the other groups together making up the remaining 26% with Lepidoptera (8%), Hymenoptera (wasps) (5%), Orthoptera (4%), Thysanoptera (2%), other Arachnida (2%) and Coleoptera (1%).

The spider species did not appear to be selective about the type of prey captured. *Thomisus stenningi* (n=43) and *T. citrinellus* (n=41), the two most abundant spider species, caught prey from all the orders while *T. daradioides* (n=35) caught prey from only the Hymenoptera (bees), Diptera and Lepidoptera.

THOMISUS DARADIOIDES

Figures 8 (A–D). A. *Thomisus daradioides*-female and male. B. Male palp. C. Epigyne. D. Eye pattern. Credits: A. Peter Webb. B & C. After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983). D. Lessert (1919).

THOMISUS STENNINGI

Figures 9 (A–D). A. *Thomisus stenningi* female. B. Male palp. C. Epigyne. D. Eye pattern. Credits: A. Peter Webb. B & C. After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983). D. Lessert (1919).

Figures 10–13. *Thomisus* spp. 10. A white *T. daradioides* female feeding on a fly (Jeremy Munton-Jackson). 11. Yellow *T. daradioides* female feeding on a bee (Allen Jones). 12. *T. stenningi* feeding on a moth (Christopher Willis). 13. *T. citrinellus* feeding on a moth (Johan van Zyl).

Huseynova (2007) studied the prey of *Thomisus onustus* and found that they are polyphagous predators, with representatives of four arthropod orders found in its diet. The primary food was Diptera and Hymenoptera, which collectively accounted for 94.2% of total prey spectrum.

PREY SIZE

As ambush predators they hide on flowers or other vegetation, patiently waiting for prey. When the opportunity arises, they will pounce on their prey with lightning-fast speed, using their front legs to grasp their target. Prey are seized, frequently from the air when 0.5-1 cm away. Although they have weak chelicerae, they secrete potent venom which allows them to attack prey larger than themselves and stop prey from struggling or flying away (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). The venom very quickly immobilizes the prey and this also allow them to catch prey up to four times their size (Fig. 14).

Figure 14. *Thomisus stenningi* female feeding on a cricket of the family Tettigoniidae (Orthoptera). Photo: Johan Gerber.

BITE SITES

The spiders usually catch their prey in the neck region (57%), 46% of prey was caught on the dorsal surface while 12% of the prey were caught in the neck from below. When the prey was caught on the abdomen, 28% of the bites were ventrally and 3% dorsally. Less than 12% of the prey was caught by the spider in the thorax region.

Bees and flies: There was an obvious difference in the bite site between the flies and bees. The bees were consistently caught in the neck region and always dorsally (76%). Otherwise they were caught ventrally on the abdomen (24%) (Figs 16–17).

The flies on the other hand were mainly caught in the abdomen. Overall, there was much more variability in the sites where flies were caught with 48% in the neck region, 31% on the abdomen and 11% on the Thorax (Figs 18–19).

Figures 15–19. *Thomisus* spp. feeding on bees and flies. 15 & 19. Bite in neck region. 16–18. Bites in abdomen. Photos: 15, 16, 18, 19. Allen Jones. 17. Hannes Mitchell.

COLOUR OF FLOWER

More than half of the spiders (53%) were the same colour as the flowers (Figs 18, 21) and 14% a close colour. Surprising, in one-third (33%) of the photographs the spiders had a different colour to the flower. This suggest that camouflage is not the only contributing factor to successful hunting.

The spiders were mainly found on white and yellow flowers (53%) of which most were daisies (42%) Most of the daisies were white or yellow with yellow centres (Figs 20–23).

Another 22% of the flowers were roses, many of which were white or pink (Figs 25–26). If cream was to be included with the white/ yellow group the total percentage of flowers in this group would be 61%. The spiders themselves on roses were predominately white (34%) or white with pink, yellow or brown markings (31%). Yellow was present in 29% and yellow with pink or brown markings 6%.

and this is usually in the centre of the flower. The spiders frequently position themselves in the centre of the flower or take up positions on the petals away from the centre. In roses and other flowers, they hide between the pedals (Figs 25–28) waiting to ambush prey. For protection, petals are sometimes pulled together with silk threads (Fig. 23).

Spiders are frequently seen covered with pollen (Fig. 24) and may play a role as a pollinator.

Figures 20–23. *Thomisus* specimens taking up different position on the flowers. 20. White spider on white petals. 21. Yellow spider on yellow flower. 22-23. Yellow spider on yellow pistil. Photos: Allen Jones.

Figure 24. *Thomisus stenningi* female covered with pollen. Photo: Allen Jones

Figures 25–28. *Thomisus* spp. 25. Female on a pink rose feeding on a fly. 26. Female on white rose preying on a fly. 27-28. Females waiting for prey. Photos: 25-27. Allen Jones. 28. Sally Adams.

POSITION ON FLOWERS

Another crucial aspect of prey capture is the exact positioning the spider takes up on the flower. Pollinators are attracted to flowers partially based on the amount of rewards that are available,

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Observations on the five-spot round-headed spider *Uroctea quinquenotata* Simon, 1910, from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: We present notes of the five-spot round-headed spiders *Uroctea quinquenotata* Simon, 1910 from South Africa. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed with notes on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

Keywords: biodiversity, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The Oecobiidae Blackwall, 1862 is a relatively small spider family, known from six genera and 127 described species distributed worldwide (World Spider Catalog, 2024). Four of the six genera (*Oecobius* Lucas, 1846; *Paroecobius* Lamoral, 1981; *Uroecobius* Kullmann & Zimmermann, 1976 and *Uroctea* Dufour, 1820) are known from South Africa. During the South African National Survey (SANSA) species of all four genera were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

Uroctea was originally a single genus of the family Urocteidae Thorell, 1869 until Lehtinen (1967) united it with genera in the family Oecobiidae Blackwall, 1862. *Uroctea* differ from Oecobiidae in being ecribellate and larger. It is represented by 20 species (World Spider Catalog, 2024) and three species *U. schinzi* Simon, 1887, *U. quinquenotata* Simon, 1910 and *U. semilimbata* Simon, 1910 are known from southern Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023).

Here we report on the five-spot round-headed spider *Uroctea quinquenotata*. They are ground dwellers found in retreats made under rocks and stones. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed with notes of their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

METHODS

Observations of the behavior of *U. quinquenotata* were carried out at Namaqua National Park (NNP), in the Northern Cape. The second author (RC) stationed at NNP, made the observations and took most of the photographs while doing research in the park. The voucher specimens sampled during SANSA are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

TAXONOMY

Uroctea quinquenotata Simon, 1910

Uroctea quinquenotata Simon, 1910: 189 (f); Tucker, 1920; Baum, 1980; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023.

Diagnostic characteristics: (Figs 1–2). Length of adult females 8–10 mm. Carapace yellow-brown, sub-circular, wider than long; with distinct clypeal snout (Fig. 3). Eight eyes with the anterior median eyes largest, remainder arranged in a compact group around them. Abdomen flattened, oval to round; slightly overlapping carapace. It is dark and decorated with five white spots (Figs 1–2); spots are usually more prominent in the young, tending to disappear in adults, but variation does occur. Anal tubercle large, 2-jointed with double row of fringed setae (Fig. 4). Legs short and sub-equal in length, the same colour as the carapace arranged star-like around the body (Fig. 2).

Figures 1–2. *Uroctea quinquenotata*. 1. Female from Soebatsfontein. 2. Immature specimen from Jakkalswater, 3 km from Nababeep. Photos: 1. Reginald Christiaan. 2. Peter Webb.

Figures 3–4. *Uroctea quinquenotata*. 3. Carapace showing the clypeal snout and eye pattern. 4. Two-jointed anal tubercle with double row of fringed setae. After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997).

Variation: Variation of abdominal patterns and shape of epigyne was observed by Tucker (1920). The testaceous spots on the abdomen are prominent in the young and tend to disappear in the adults. However, the range of variation is such that they may be retained in adult forms and even reinforced by testaceous flecks, until the spots are linked in an irregular chain. Also, almost melanistic varieties occur, the upper abdomen lacking testaceous spots or flecks. Alternatively a paler abdomen and more testaceous above, the spots joined together and the abdomen ventrally pale.

Figures 5–8. *Uroctea quinquenotata*. 5. Female ventral view. 6. Abdomen ventral view. 7–8. Female dorsal view. Photos: 5–7. A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 8. Charles Haddad.

Epigyne: Tucker (1920) provided a drawing of the epigyne seen in spirits (Fig. 9). He however found exceptions to occur in the shape of the epigyne with the two lateral sides sometimes situated closer together and coalesced, to join to form a dark band. He speculated that the variations seem due to the internal arrangement of the spermathecae showing through the vulval plates in a slightly different fashion.

Baum (1980) provided drawings of the epigyne of *U. quinquenotata* based on material from MNHN (4395) and SAM (3865). It is doubtful that the specimens from MNHN, that were sampled in 1904 from Steinkopf and Komaggas in the Northern Cape, are the type specimens as stated by Simon (1910). His drawing (Fig. 10) differs from that of Tucker (1920) with epigynal opening only a narrow slit.

The epigyne of a *Uroctea* specimens sampled from the same area as the type locality resemble more that of Tucker (1920)(Fig. 11).

Only the females of the southern African species have been described and there seems to be some variation in colour and the shape of the epigyne. Only with the description of the males the diagnostic characteristics of the different species would become clear.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Northern Cape: Augrabies National Park (-28.53, 20.29); Komaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 17.17); Sendelingsdrif (-28.13, 16.90); Namaqua National Park (-30.011, 17.580); Soebatsfontein (-30.11, 17.59); Jakkalswater near Nababeep (-29.623, 17.823). **Western Cape:** Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); Swartberg Nature Reserve, Gamkaskloof (-33.35, 21.67); Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.51, 19.29); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 643 m a.s.l. (-32.396, 19.087); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 677 m a.s.l. (-32.397, 19.087); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 1152 m a.s.l. (-32.461, 19.239); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 1366 m a.s.l. (-32.435, 19.213); Cederberg, Crystal Pools, 927 m a.s.l. (-32.310, 19.174); Cederberg, Crystal Pools, 920 m a.s.l. (-32.310, 19.175); Cederberg, Driehoek, 919 m a.s.l. (-32.424, 19.163); Cederberg, Niewoudts Pass, 527 m a.s.l. (-32.350, 19.007); Cederberg, Wupperthal, 524 m a.s.l. (-32.278, 19.219); Laingsburg (-33.20, 20.85).

Map showing distribution of *Uroctea quinquenotata*.

HABITAT

This family is highly adaptable to more arid and semi-arid habitats. The species was sampled from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Nama Karoo, Succulent and Desert Biomes. In the fynbos in the Cederberg Wilderness Area, the species was sampled from 524– 1152 m a.s.l. with pitfall traps (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2016).

BEHAVIOUR

They are ground dwellers that make a dome-shaped retreat under stones (Figs 13, 14). Only when turning the stone the retreat is visible. The retreat consists of multi-layered sheets (Fig. 17) with stiff guy threads radiating in all directions. The retreat is attached to the stone with a flat part facing the stone (Fig. 16), and the dome-shaped part facing the ground. The round, scalloped edge is attached to the stone with stiff guy threads radiating in all directions. Small objects such as stones and bits of debris are frequently attached to the retreat (Fig. 15). When removing the retreat (Figs 19–21) the spider can be seen lying on its back. Prey carcasses around the retreat were mainly that of ants. In the evening, they left the retreat and wander around in search of food. They have been found entering houses.

VENOM

The SANSA identification service received a photo of *U. quinquenotata* (Fig. 12) that has bit a person in a house in the Cederberg at night. There was immediately a burning pain, and the burning was present until the next day. The area was red and slightly swollen, but no further symptoms developed.

Figures 13–24. *Uroctea quinquenotata*. 13. Stones under which retreats are found. 14. Turned stone showing dome shaped part of retreat. 15. Dome part of retreat covered with debris. 16. When pulling the dome the guy threads visible. 17. Retreat with multi layer sheets. 18. Spider laying on its back in retreat. 19–21. Opened retreat. 22–24. Egg sac with first-instar spiderlings.

Spindle-shaped white egg sacs (Fig. 22) were found in the retreats (January-February). The sacs were well protected, and several silk layers needed to be removed to access the sacs. On closer inspections (February), the first instar spiderlings could be seen through the silk layer. (Figs 22, 23). Twelve first-instar spiderlings were counted from an egg sac removed in February (Figs 23, 24).

CONSERVATION

The species has been sampled from Northern and Western Cape It is protected in the Augrabies National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021), Benfontein Nature Reserve, Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2016), Richtersveld Trans-frontier National Park, Namaqua National Park and Swartberg Nature Reserve. There are no known threats therefore listed as Least Concern. However, additional sampling is required to collect and describe the male of *U. quinquenotata*.

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Notes on the false button spider *Steatoda capensis* Hann, 1990 in South Africa (Araneae: Theridiidae)

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ABSTRACT: The false button spider *Steatoda capensis* was described as *Teutana lepida* by O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 from the Cape Peninsula. As the name *lepida* was preoccupied, a replacement name *Steatoda capensis* was provided. The species is known from southern Africa but was introduced to St. Helena, Australia, New Zealand and Hawaii. The general morphology of both sexes of the species is discussed, as well as the colour variations with photographs of live specimens and notes on their lifestyle and distribution in South Africa. Although not severe, *S. capensis* can produce a painful bite.

Keywords: agroecosystems, agrobiont, behaviour, biodiversity, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Steatoda* Sundevall, 1833 is known from 120 species and subspecies (World Spider Catalog, 2024). From South Africa nine species has so far been identified (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), specimens from several South African localities (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) have been sampled. This includes several species of *Steatoda*. They are often mistaken for the more venomous button spiders (*Latrodectus* spp.), hence their common name, the false button spider.

Steatoda capensis was described as *Teutana lepida* by O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 from Cape Peninsula. As the name *lepida* was preoccupied, Hann (1990) provided a replacement name *Steatoda capensis*. According to Hann (1990), this species is endemic to southern Africa but has spread to New Zealand, where it now occurs widely around beaches, gardens, and houses, displacing the endemic New Zealand species *Latrodectus katipo*. The species was also introduced to St. Helena, Australia, New Zealand and Hawaii (World Spider Catalog, 2024). Hann (1990) reported that specimens were also collected from containers originating from Australia and the U.S.A. Most of the Old-World species have not been revised since their original description.

MORPHOLOGY

They are medium to large spiders with a total length of females 7.0–8.8 mm and the males 5.7–7.2 mm. In the female the body is usually purplish black usually with a white band around the anterior edge of the abdomen, with additional dorsal patterns of lines and spots (Figs 1, 4), patterns sometimes faint or absent (Fig. 2). Carapace longer than wide and with a distinct fovea; lateral eyes touching or separated by less than their diameter. Abdomen sub-oval. venter either black or brown, or with a white spot behind the epigastric furrow. On the underside is a central reddish and one or two other white spots (Fig. 9) (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904).

In males, the carapace is rugose, with stridulatory ridges on the posterior sides of the carapace and sclerotized ridges around the pedicel (Figs 3, 5; chelicerae with 1 or 2 teeth on anterior margin; abdomen white band around anterior edge of the abdomen but sometimes band pale yellow (Fig. 3), venter either black or brown. Genitalia (Figs 6, 7) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

Variation: O. Pickard-Cambridge (1904) in his description of the species collected in the Cape Peninsula reported that the females have a red patch on the underside of the abdomen. This resulted in *S. capensis* being known locally in the Cape Peninsula in South Africa as the "knoppie spider", because of the red marking under the abdomen.

Figures 1–3. *Steatoda capensis*. 1. Female dorsal view, showing the markings on the abdomen. 2. Female from Uniondale ventral view showing the red marking. 3. Male dorsal view with yellow anterior band. Photos: 1, 3 Peter Webb. 2. Joy Paton.

Figures 4–6. *Steatoda capensis*. 4. Female. 5. Male. 6. Epigyne. 7. Palp. Photos: A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

However in specimens sampled in the northern part of the country, the red marking was absent (Fig. 8). A recent specimen photographed from a farm along de Hoop road, near Uniondale in the Western Cape by the second author showed the presence of the red marking (Fig. 9).

LIFESTYLE

They build their webs beneath logs, stones, and other debris, under bark or in crevices in boulders, rock faces, and tree trunks up to a height of 2 m. The commonest form of the web is an irregular tangle of white threads that cover the surrounding substrate up to a radius of 0,5 m. An ill-defined opening (about 2 cm in diameter) at the base of the web leads to a retreat. Daylight hours are usually spent in the retreat while the spider moves more to the front during the night to hunt. They overwinter in various stages of development, including the adult stage. The white slightly fluffy egg sac is attached to the web (Figs 10–11).

HABITAT

The species was sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Thicket biomes. The species was also sampled from crops such as maize, pear, tomatoes, pine plantations and vineyards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Steatoda capensis is commonly found throughout South Africa (Map 1). It is also a common species recorded in and around houses (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Müller, 1990). It was originally collected on the Cape Peninsula, Cape Flats, Possession Island and at Rooibank near Walvis Bay. However, during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, (2015) the species was sampled from all nine provinces (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023) (Map 1).

Map 1. *Steatoda capensis* distribution in South Africa.

Figures 8–11. *Steatoda capensis*. 8. Female without ventral markings. 9. Female from Uniondale with red ventral marking. 10-11. Female in nest with egg sacs from Uniondale. Photos: Joy Payton.

TOXICITY

Steatoda is a sister group to *Latrodectus* which possesses the highly potent neurotoxins called α -latrotoxins that can induce neuromuscular paralysis and are responsible for human fatalities.

Little is known about the potential toxicity of *Steatoda* to man (Maretic *et al.*, 1964; Maretic, 1978). Research undertaken by Grasso (1987) has shown that the venom of *S. paykulliana* (Walckenaer, 1806) has low toxicity to mammals but extremely high toxicity to insects. In Ireland and the UK *S. nobilis* (Thorell, 1875) was identified as a medically significant spider, as envenomation have resulted in local and systemic neurotoxic symptoms similar to true black widows (genus *Latrodectus*) (Dunbar, 2018).

In South Africa, an investigation into *Steatoda* venom investigated the relative toxicity of *Latrodectus indistinctus*, *L. geometricus* and *Steatoda foravae* in laboratory mice (Müller *et al.*, 1992). It showed that *S. foravae* is at least 10-12 times less venomous than the black widow, *L. indistinctus*. From a medical point of view, its toxicity is therefore relatively unimportant. However, since it is often mistaken for the black widow, it still has some medical relevance.

It was in Australia, where *S. capensis* is now commonly found, that human bites were reported to cause a syndrome known as steatodism; which has been described as a less severe form latrodectism. Bites are quite painful and can cause a general malaise for about a day, localized pain, and redness around the bite, but may also include nausea and headaches. (Isbister & Gray, 2003). In severe cases, the clinical effects were almost indistinguishable from *Latrodectus*, except diaphoresis was absent, and the spiders were often mistaken for *Latrodectus*. Bites are predominantly inflicted by females, but males also have the potential to bite.

So, when the locals in the Cape Peninsula dreaded *S. capensis* bites according to O. Pickard-Cambridge (1904) they were not completely wrong. He wrote that local cases of serious illness and death were attributed to its bite, but another culprit causing the problems was later identified as *Latrodectus indistinctus*, a member of the Black Widow group (Smithers, 1944).

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Observation on the stone huntsman spider *Eusparassus schoemanae* Moradmand, 2013 (Araneae: Sparassidae)

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ABSTRACT: The stone huntsman spider *Eusparassus schoemanae* Moradmand, 2013 an endemic Southern Africa species is discussed. The general morphology of the species is discussed, and photographs of live specimens are provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in Southern Africa, and conservation status and threats are provided.

Keywords: distribution, biodiversity, new records, Conservation status, threads.

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), a large number of Sparassidae species were recorded (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). As part of SANSA surveys, requests were made for photographs of species for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) and a large number of photographs were received from the public. This include information on the genus *Eusparassus* Simon, 1903.

Moradmand (2013) provided an overview of all the known species of the genus *Eusparassus* that is represented by 33 species. They are small to very large huntsman spiders distributed in Africa and Eurasia. He described three new species: *E. borakalalo*; *E. jaegeri* and *E. schoemanae* from South Africa.

The aim of this paper is to present additional information on *E. schoemanae*. It is a southern African species mainly known from the Northern Cape and Namibia. Notes are provided on their morphology, behaviour, distribution, conservation status and possible threat.

METHODS

Specimens collected during SANSA surveys were deposited as voucher specimens in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division .

TAXONOMY

Eusparassus schoemanae Moradmand, 2013

Eusparassus schoemanae Moradmand, 2013: 53 (m,f); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022.

Description: Small sized; total length: 8.5–10 mm. Carapace and legs uniformly pale creamy yellow; abdomen more yellow brown, elongate, dorsally with a median band with small spots (Fig. 1) or faint chevrons (Fig. 2). Female epigyne and medium septum elongate (Fig. 4). Male palp with cymbium approximately twice as long as tibia (Figs 5 & 6); tegulum and subtegulum bulged and expanded, dorsal retrotibial apophysis pointing distad and ventral retro tibial apophysis hump-like (Figs 5 & 6).

Figures 1–2. Two *Eusparassus schoemanae* females from Uniondale, Western Cape. Photo credits: Joy Paton.

Figures 3–7. *Eusparassus schoemanae*. 3. Habitus female from Nigramoep. 4. Epigyne. 5 & 6. Male palp 7. Female from Namibia. Photos: 3-4. Charles Haddad. 5-6. After Moradmand (2013). 7. Anka Eichhoff.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Namibia: Kunene region Farm Otjitambi near Otjikondo (-19.48, 15.11); Karas Region near Kodaspiek. **South Africa: Northern Cape:** Lieliefontein (-30.3, 18.07); Farm Loeriesfontein, Aberdeen, Great Karroo (-30.95, 19.45); Calvinia, 10 km N of Loeriesfontein (-30.58, 19.26); Kamiesberg Mountain, 22–24 km E of Kamieskroon (-30.3, 19.08); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Kgala-gadi Transfrontier Park (-25.48, 20.24); Tswalu Nature Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Nigramoep (-29.53, 17.58); Jakkalswater Guest Farm near Nababeep (-29.59, 17.78). **Western Cape:** Clanwilliam, Doorn Bosch (-31.56, 19.15); Clanwilliam, Pakhuys (-32.06, 19.05); Clanwilliam, Groot Fontein (-32.04, 18.39); Uniondale (-33.66, 23.13) (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Map showing the distribution of *Eusparassus schoemanae* in South Africa.

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-living nocturnal ground dwellers. During the day they hide in silk retreats made on the underside of stones or in crevices of rocks (Figs 9, 10). The spiders make their retreats under big flattish stones lying on the ground, at least with one flat surface on the underside. When turning the stone the white silk retreats are clearly visible attached to the stone. When opening the sac retreat the spider found inside (Fig. 11). Frequently more than one retreat are found in the same area (Fig. 9). The retreats are also used to moult and deposit the egg sac (Fig. 11). Females construct a sealed egg-sac inside the larger retreat and guard it until the spiderlings hatch.

HABITAT

The species is sampled from the Desert, Succulent Karoo and Grassland biomes (Haddad *et al.* 2013). They are mainly collected by hand but some males (Fig. 12) run around and land in pitfall or malaise traps.

Figure 9–14. *Eusparassus schoemanae*. 9. Retreats made under stones in Uniondale area. 10. Stone nests retreat from Namibia. 11. Female in opened retreat from Namibia. 12. Female from Jakkalswater in the Northern Cape. Photos: 10-11. Anka Eichhoff. 14. Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION

The species is known from several localities in Namibia- and South Africa. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of least concern. A possible threat has been identified by the second author. Baboons are known to turn stones in search of food. Frequently she found loose stones were turned upside down and a complete absence of spiders or insects. Therefore, in areas where baboons are present, they might be a threat to spiders and other invertebrates.

In South Africa the species receive protection in areas such as the Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park; Benfontein Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2023); Kgalagadi Transfrontier Park and Tswalu Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2016).

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Observation of the green hairy field spider *Neoscona rufipalpis* (Lucas, 1858) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Neoscona rufipalpis* (Lucas, 1858) was one of the Araneidae species sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA). It is a species with a wide global distribution throughout the Afrotropical Region. Observations on their behaviour, colour variation and distribution are discussed.

Keywords: behaviour, biodiversity, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

Neoscona rufipalpis is an African species described by Lucas (1858) as *Epeira rufipalpis* from Gabon. The species has a very wide global distribution throughout the Afrotropical Region. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) specimens from several localities in South Africa were sampled and photographed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). With all the specimens available the variation in colour in the females became eminent. This variation might explain why Strand (1908) described four varieties of *Aranea rufipalpis* from Africa but only *Neoscona rufipalpis buettnerana* Strand, 1908) is recognized from Cameroon and Togo (World Spider Catalog, 2024).

The presence of *N. rufipalpis* in South Africa is discussed, with notes on their colour variation and morphology based on live photographs. Information on their behaviour, distribution and conservation in South Africa is provided.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens sampled during the SANSA surveys deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA) were examined. As part of SANSA requests were made for photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum and several were received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Neoscona rufipalpis (Lucas, 1858)

Epeira rufipalpis Lucas, 1858: 422 (f); Grasshoff, 1986: 73(mf); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 13.

Diagnostic characters: The female *N. rufipalpis* is a medium-sized (11–13 mm) orb weaver easily recognised by the round abdomen. The female carapace is dark, with a layer of white setae (Fig. 1). The abdomen is as wide as long, slightly flattened dorsally, with faint transverse bands (Fig. 2). The transverse bands in some specimens are more distinct (Fig. 3). The folium pattern common in *Neoscona* species is absent, apodemes with dark spots (Fig. 4). Abdomen colour varied from green (Figs 1 & 4) to yellow-brown (Figs 6 & 7) to creamy grey (Figs 2 & 5). Thin dark lines and markings are present on the anterior border of the abdomen (Fig. 21).

Figures 1–7. *Neoscona rufipalpis* females. 1. From Addo National Park (Linda Wiese). 2. Irene (Peter Webb). 3. Isimangolisa Wetlands (Ruan Booysen). 4. Pretoria (Vida vd Walt). 5–7. From Kwamalanga (Peter Webb).

Figures 8–12. *Neoscona rufipalpis*. 8. Male habitus. 9. Female habitus. 10–11. Epigyne. 12. Female ventral view. Credits: 8–10. Drawings after Grasshoff (1986). 11–12. Peter Webb.

The sternum is yellow and there are four yellow spots on the abdomen ventrally (Fig. 12). Legs are the same colour as the carapace with only leg IV distinctly banded (Figs 5 & 7). The female has a long scape as shown in Figs 10–12. The male is much smaller (5–11 mm), abdomen oval shaped with faint dark markings (Fig. 8).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Neoscona rufipalpis is an African endemic species that was described from São Tomé and has been collected from Cape Verde, St Helena, Yemen [mainland Socotra] and several countries in the Afrotropical Region (World Spider Catalog, 2024). In South Africa it is common and has been collected from seven provinces (Fig. 13). For details on locality data see Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2022).

Figure 13. Known distribution of *Neoscona rufipalpis* in South Africa.

BEHAVIOUR

The spiders are found in a tightly woven funnel retreat made of silk. They are frequently found in broad-leaved trees. The orb-web connected with the retreat is constructed in front of the retreat consisting of widely-spaced spirals made of golden, sticky silk (Figs 14–17). Unlike other *Neoscona* species that make orb-webs overnight and remove them in the morning, *N. rufipalpis* only repairs the web when needed. They are active at night (Figs 18–20) but are found during the day in the retreat.

HABITAT

The species have been sampled from most of the floral biomes but were absent from the Succulent and Nama Karoo and Desert. As a predator, they play an important role in agro-ecosystems and prey on a wide variety of insects (Fig. 21) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) and were sampled from avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), citrus (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2001) and macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001).

Figures 14–17. *Neoscona rufipalpis* funnel retreat made in citrus tree with orb-web during the day. Photos: Chantall Strumpher.

Figures 18–19. *Neoscona rufipalpis* female in retreat. 19. Female with egg sac in back ground. 20. Female active in web at night. Photos: Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION STATUS

Neoscona rufipalpis has a wide global distribution. There are no significant threats to the species and it is listed as Least Concern. In South Africa it is protected in the seven protected areas.

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Figure 21. *Neoscona rufipalpis* female in golden web feeding. Photo: Peter Webb.

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A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve, South Africa

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ABSTRACT: A checklist of the spiders from the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve in the Gauteng Province, South Africa, is provided. The checklist was compiled South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) database. A total of 245 species from 40 families and 161 genera are presently protected in the reserve. The most species-rich families are the Salticidae (25 spp.), Thomisidae (37 spp.), and Araneidae (28 spp.), while 15 families are represented by singletons. The global distribution, endemism, and conservation status for each species are provided. Most species (97%) have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern, two species are Data Deficient, and four species are of Special Concern. Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve is a type locality for twelve new species.

Key words: conservation, endemism, Savanna Biome, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA).

INTRODUCTION

The aim of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) is to document the Arachnida fauna of South Africa. Extensive surveys were undertaken to obtain species-specific information and to identify new, rare, and endemic species (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015, Foord *et al.*, 2020). Inventories in protected areas provide information on species already protected.

Gauteng is the smallest province, covering only 1.4% of South Africa. It falls within both the Savanna and highly threatened Grassland Biome with approximately 83% of the province falling within the Highveld Grassland vegetation type, of which a mere 0.8% is currently conserved in South Africa (Pfab, 2001).

As part of SANSA all known data was collated into a database. Extensive sampling took place in the Gauteng province (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014) but only a few of the surveys have been published. Presently, 563 spider species are known from this small province (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). Published surveys are the Roodeplaat Research Station (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1979), Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989), Rietondale Research Station (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991), Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022), Groenkloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023) and the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl, 2023).

The current checklist presents the results of all the spiders sampled from the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve in Gauteng Province. The reserve is situated 32 km north-east of Pretoria. Several surveys in the reserve have been undertaken since 1915.

The first checklist based on material sampled by National Collection of Arachnida staff over a period of 4 years (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989) listed only 110 species. This updated spider checklist list 245 species. Owen (2010) has stressed the importance of continued long-term monitoring when assessing the diversity, particularly for invertebrates whose populations show major inter-seasonal and inter-annual fluctuations. Specimens sampled in the RDNR were used during taxonomic revisions resulting in the recognition of twelve new species from the reserve.

Figures 1–3. Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve. 1. Entrance. 2–3. Some of the habitat types. Photos: Peter Webb.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: The Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (RDNR) (28°22'S, 25°37'E) is situated 32 km north-east of Pretoria, 1 225 m above sea level. The reserve has a sub-tropical climate with a wet summer (average rainfall of 686 mm) and a dry winter. Rainfall records kept since October 1949 indicate that the rainy season starts in November, maximum rainfall occurs in November and January, and little or no rain falls from May to August. The mean annual temperature is 18,2°C with the highest maximum temperature recorded at 37,4°C and the lowest minimum at 6,7°C.

The nature reserve is generally a rather open savanna with *Senegalia caffra* the dominant tree, in a tall and dense grass veld dominated by *Cymbopogon plurinodis*, *Themeda triandra*, *Elinurus argenteus*, and *Hypparrhenia* spp. Acocks (1975) classified the veld as Veld Type 19 (Sourish Mixed Bushveld) which often occurs as an irregular belt on gentle mountain slopes between grassveld and bushveld.

Sampling efforts: Different surveys were undertaken by the staff of the Ditsong Museum (previously Transvaal Museum), staff of the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council, and staff of the Gauteng Department of Agriculture and Rural Development (GDACE) (Table 1). The voucher specimens are housed in the Ditsong Museum and the NCA.

Conservation status: The conservation status of each species was derived from a recent National Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020) where spatial analysis on observed occurrences using functions for Extent of Occurrence (EOO), Area of Occupancy (AOO), and elevational range the area of occupation was determined. The assumed knowledge of the full range for all species based on their observed occurrences, and EOO was calculated as the minimum convex polygon around all occurrences, and the 2 km² cells occupied were used to calculate AOO. The distribution of threats across lineages was visualized using a mosaic plot, with the size of rectangles representing the proportion of species in a specific family represented within four categories: Data Deficient (DD), Least Concern (LC), Endangered (EN) and Vulnerable (VU) (Foord *et al.*, 2020) (Table 3).

Endemicity value: The global distribution of each species was provided to determine the endemicity value of each species (Table 4). Values used to indicate species endemicity (E):

6 – only known from the type locality (RDNR); 5 – known from several localities in Gauteng (GE); 4 – known from Gauteng as well as an adjacent province; 3 – known from more than two provinces in South Africa (SAE); 2 – known from other Southern African countries (STHE); 1 – known from other countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE); 0 – also from countries outside the Afrotropical Region (CE).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Diversity

A total of 245 species in 161 genera and 40 families were recorded (Tables 2 & Appendix 1). The most species-rich families were the Salticidae (45 spp.), Thomisidae (37 spp.) and Araneidae (28 spp.), while 15 families were represented by singletons. It compares well with the diversity of Kgaswane Mountain Reserve, in North West where a total of 222 species from 40 families and 152 genera were collected. Sampling in both the RDNR and Kgaswane Mountain Reserve were undertaken from 1980 to 1983 beating and sweeping the vegetation (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

Table 1. Surveys undertaken at the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve.

SURVEYS	DATE	MUS	REFERENCES
Ditsong Museum staff (then Transvaal Museum TM)	1915 (Hand)	TM	Van Dam & Roberts, 1917
National Collection of Arachnida staff	1980 to 1983 (Beating & sweeping)	NCA	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 1989
Gauteng Department of Agriculture and Rural Development (GDACE) staff	2010-2018 (Pitfall traps)	NCA	SANSA database
Ian Engelbrecht(GDACE) field staff	2008 to 2009 (Pitfall traps)	TM	Engelbrecht, 2013
SANSA Surveys	2014 (Hand)	NCA	SANSA database

TABLE 2. Spider diversity of the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve, with total number of families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP.) sampled.

FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	FAMILY	GEN	SPP.
Agelenidae	1	1	Oonopidae	1	1
Araneidae	20	28	Oxyopidae	3	9
Atypidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Bemmeridae	1	1	Philodromidae	4	8
Caponiidae	1	1	Pholcidae	1	1
Cheiracanthiidae	1	5	Phyxelididae	1	1
Clubionidae	1	2	Pisauridae	8	8
Corinnidae	2	2	Salticidae	25	45
Ctenidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Cyrtacheniidae	1	3	Segestriidae	1	1
Deinopidae	1	1	Selenopidae	2	3
Dictynidae	2	2	Sparassidae	3	3
Eresidae	2	3	Stasimopidae	1	3
Gnaphosidae	7	10	Tetragnathidae	2	7
Hersiliidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	3	3
Idiopidae	5	7	Theridiidae	10	12
Linyphiidae	8	9	Thomisidae	17	37
Lycosidae	10	12	Trachelidae	3	3
Nesticidae	1	1	Uloboridae	2	2
Oecobiidae	1	1	Zodariidae	4	4
			40 families	161	245

Spiders collected at the RDNR have been included in several revisionary studies. Undetermined species in the previous checklist (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989) are now identified to species level. The twelve new species are indicted with an asterisk in Appendix 1.

Due to the sampling effort of the staff of the Ditsong Museum (Van Dam & Roberts, 1916) 17 Mygalomorphae species have been recorded. Many of these species were described by the arachnologist John Hewitt stationed at that museum during that period. In total he has described 23 Mygalomorphae species between 1910–1923 fromGauteng.

Figures 4–8. Tetragnathidae species recorded from the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve. 4. *Tetragnatha subsquamata*. 5. *T. nitens*. 6. *T. demissa*. 7. *Leucauge festiva*. 8. *L. decorata*. Photos: Peter Webb.

The reserve is situated next to the Roodeplaatdam and seven Tetragnathidae species were sampled (Figs 4–6). This is more species usually recorded during Gauteng surveys. The *Tetragnatha* species sampled were examined and included in the Okuma & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1988) review. While sampling in the summer, the *Tetragnatha* spiders were very abundant on *Senegalia caffra* and more than a hundred specimens were collected during each collection trip.

Conservation status

Of the 245 species sampled, 0.8% are Data Deficient (DD), i.e. lacking taxonomic or distribution data, while two species were not evaluated (NE), indicating possible new species or species only sampled from juveniles. The majority (237) species have a wide distribution and are listed as being of Least Concern (LC).

Of the four species of special concern, one *Galeosoma hirsutum* Hewitt, 1916 (Figs 9–10) is Endangered (EN) and three species are Vulnerable: *Idiops pretoriae* (Pocock, 1898) (Fig. 11); *Calommata transvaalica* Hewitt, 1916 (Figs 11–12) and *Stasimopus hewitti* Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012 (Fig. 13) (Table 3; Appendix 1).

TABLE 3: Conservation status and of the spider species sampled at the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve.

CONSERVATION STATUS	SPP.	%
Data deficient (DD)	2	0.8
Not evaluated (NE)	2	0.8
Least concern (LC)	237	96.7
Endangered (EN)	1	0.4
Vulnerable (VU)	3	1.22

***Galeosoma hirsutum* Hewitt, 1916 (Idiopidae)**

A Gauteng endemic described by Hewitt (1916) from Roodeplaat. This species is known from fewer than five extant locations and is threatened throughout its range by urban development.

It therefore qualifies for listing as Endangered under criterion B (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021a) (Figs 9).

Figures 9–10. *Galeosoma hirsutum* female. Photo: A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

***Idiops pretoriae* (Pocock, 1898) (Idiopidae)**

A Gauteng endemic described by Pocock (1898) as *Acanthodon pretoriae*. The material old and sampled prior to 1898. The species is recorded from several localities around Pretoria in Gauteng. It has lost most of its habitat to urban development, and loss of habitat is ongoing. With between five and 10 extant locations this species qualifies as Vulnerable under criterion B. (Fig. 11) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021a).

Figure 11. *Idiops pretoriae* male. Photo: Jonathan Leeming.

***Calommata transvaalica* Hewitt, 1916 (Atypidae)**

A South African endemic described from Roodeplaat. It is known only from the Gauteng and Limpopo provinces (Soutpansberg and Blouberg). Parts of its habitat have been threatened in Gauteng due to crop cultivation and urban development. The species is suspected to occur at fewer than 10 locations. It is therefore listed as Vulnerable under the B criterion (Figs 12–13) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022)

Figures 11–12. *Calommata transvaalica*. 12. Female. 13. Male. Photos: Charles Haddad.

Stasimopus hewitti Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012 (Stasimopidae)

A Gauteng endemic described from the Wonderboom district. Presently recorded from only seven locations. There is ongoing loss of habitat within this species range to urbanization, and it is therefore listed as Vulnerable under the B criterion (Fig. 14). (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021b).

Figure 14. *Stasimopus hewitti* male. Photo: David Jacobs.

TABLE 4. Endemicity of the spider species sampled at the Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve.

ENDEMICITY	SPP.	%
0 – Africa and wider (C)	31	12.7
1 – African endemics (AE)	115	46.9
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	48	19.6
3 – SA endemics (SAE)	43	17.6
4 – SA (SAE): 2 adjacent provinces	1	0.4
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)	4	1.6
6 – Known only from type locality	1	0.4

Endemicity

Of the species identified to species level only 43 (17.6%) are South African endemics; 46.9% are African endemics and 19.6% are Southern African endemics while 31 species has a distribution wider than Africa (Table 4; Appendix 1).

Only one Linyphiidae species *Callitrichia minuta* (Jocqué, 1984) is endemic to the RDNR and the four species of Special Concern are Gauteng endemics.

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Mahemba hewitti (Araneidae)

Prasonica albolimbata (Araneidae)

Hyposinga lithyphantoides (Araneidae)

Caponia chelifera (Caponiidae)

Copuetta lacustris (Corinnidae)

Aphantaulax inornata (Gnaphosidae)

Ctenolophus fenoulheti (Idiopidae)

Ostearius melanopygius (Linyphiidae)

Allocosa excerta (Lycosidae)

Allocosa lawrencei (Lycosidae)

Evippomma squamulatum (Lycosidae)

Hippasa australis (Lycosidae)

Oxyopes longispinosus (Oxyopidae)

Oxyopes bothai (Oxyopidae)

Peucetia striata

Photos: Peter Webb

Thanatus dorsilineatus (Philodromidae)

Rothus aethiopicus (Pisauridae)

Vidole sothoana (Phyxelididae)

Mogrus mathisi (Salticidae)

Pellenes bulawayoensis (Salticidae)

Vicirionessa mustela (Salticidae)

Tusitala barbata (Salticidae)

Olios correvoni nigrifrons (Sparassidae)

Enoplognatha inornata (Theridiidae)

Camaricus nigrotesselatus (Thomisidae)

Thomisops pupa (Thomisidae)

Tmarus cameliformis (Thomisidae)

Miagrammopes brevicaudus (Uloboridae)

Capheris decorata (Zodariidae)

Systemoplacis vandami (Zodariidae)

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), country endemism (CEND)
LC Least Concern, DD Data Deficient, VU Vulnerable, NE Not Evaluated, EN Endangered * species described from Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve

FAMILY/ SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	FAMILY/ SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
FAMILY AGELENIDAE				FAMILY CORINNIDAE			
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE
FAMILY ARANEIDAE				<i>Copuetta lacustris</i> (Strand, 1916)	1	LC	AE
<i>Araneus apricus</i> (Karsch, 1884)	1	LC	AE	FAMILY CTENIDAE			
<i>Argiope aurocincta</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE	<i>Ctenus transvaalensis</i> Benoit, 1981	3	LC	SAE
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	FAMILY CYRTAUCHENIIDAE			
<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Ancylotrypa brevipalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916) *	3	LC	SAE
<i>Caerostris corticosa</i> Pocock, 1902	2	LC	STHE	<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	<i>Ancylotrypa rufescens</i> (Hewitt, 1916) *	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	FAMILY DEINOPIIDAE			
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C	FAMILY DICTYNIDAE			
<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	<i>Archaeodictyna conducta</i> (O.Pickard-Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C
<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE	<i>Dictyna</i> sp. (Undetermined)			NE
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	FAMILY ERESIDAE			
<i>Lipocrea longissima</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
<i>Mahemba hewitti</i> (Lessert, 1930)	1	LC	AE	<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE
<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Stegodyphus mimosarum</i> Pavesi, 1883	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	FAMILY GNAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	0	LC	C	<i>Ammoxenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	<i>Aphantaulax inornata</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	0	LC	C	<i>Drassodes ereptor</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Pararaneus spectator</i> (Karsch, 1885)	0	LC	C	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
<i>Prasonica albolimbata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus anthropoides</i> Hewitt, 1916 *	3	LC	SAE
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Singa lawrencei</i> (Lessert, 1930)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	FAMILY HERSILIIDAE			
<i>Zygiella x-notata</i> (Clerck, 1757)	0	LC	C	<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY ATYPIDAE				FAMILY IDIOPIDAE			
<i>Calommata transvaalica</i> Hewitt, 1916 *	4	VU	SAE	<i>Ctenolophus cregoei</i> (Purcell, 1902)	3	LC	SAE
FAMILY BEMMERIDAE				<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE
<i>Homostola vulpecula</i> Simon, 1892	3	LC	SAE	<i>Galeosoma hirsutum</i> Hewitt, 1916 *	5	EN	SAE
FAMILY CAPONIIDAE				<i>Gorgyrella schreineri minor</i> (Hewitt, 1916) *	3	LC	SAE
<i>Caponia chelifera</i> Lessert, 1936	2	LC	STHE	<i>Idiops fryi</i> (Purcell, 1903)	3	LC	SAE
FAMILY CHEIRACANTHIIDAE				<i>Idiops pretoriae</i> (Pocock, 1898)	5	VU	SAE
<i>Cheiracanthium aculeatum</i> Simon, 1884	1	LC	AE	<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	FAMILY LINYPHIIDAE			
<i>Cheiracanthium dippenaarae</i> Lotz, 2007 *	3	DD	SAE	<i>Agyneta prosectes</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	<i>Agyneta prosectoides</i> (Locket & Russell-Smith, 1980)	1	LC	AE
<i>Cheiracanthium vansoni</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE	<i>Callitrichia minuta</i> (Jocqué, 1984)	6	DDT	SAE
FAMILY CLUBIONIDAE				<i>Mermessus fradeorum</i> (Berland, 1932)	0	LC	C
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Clubiona revillioi</i> Lessert, 1936	2	LC	STHE				

FAMILY/ SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	FAMILY/ SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.Pickard-Cambridge, 1880)	0	LC	C	FAMILY PISAURIDAE			
<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE	<i>Afropisaura rothiformis</i> (Strand, 1908)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pseudomicrocentria minutissima</i> Miller, 1970	1	LC	AE	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tybaertiella krugeri</i> (Simon, 1894)	1	LC	AE	<i>Euprosthénops proximus</i> Lessert, 1916	1	LC	AE
FAMILY LYCOSIDAE				<i>Euprosthénopsis vuattouxi</i> Blandin, 1977	1	LC	AE
<i>Allocosa exserta</i> Roewer, 1959	2	LC	STHE	<i>Maypaciús christophei</i> Blandin, 1975	1	LC	AE
<i>Allocosa lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Nilus margaritatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
<i>Amblyothele ecologica</i> Russell-Smith, Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2009	3	LC	SAE	<i>Perenethis simoni</i> (Lessert, 1916)	1	LC	AE
<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE	FAMILY SALTICIDAE			
<i>Hippasosa guttata</i> (Karsch, 1878)	1	LC	AE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna zuluana</i> Roewer, 1959	3	LC	SAE	<i>Belippo meridionalis</i> Wesotowska & Haddad, 2013	3	LC	SAE
<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	<i>Dendryphantes hararensis</i> Wesotowska & Cumming, 2008	2	LC	STHE
<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Evarcha flagellaris</i> Haddad & Wesotowska, 2011	1	LC	AE
<i>Proevippa hirsuta</i> (Russell-Smith, 1981)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Evarcha striolata</i> Wesotowska & Haddad, 2009	3	LC	SAE
<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE	<i>Festucula leroyae</i> Azarkina & Foord, 2014 *	2	LC	STHE
<i>Wadicosa oncka</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	1	LC	AE	<i>Helafricanus debilis</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
FAMILY NESTICIDAE				<i>Helafricanus fasciatus</i> (Wesotowska, 1986)	1	LC	AE
<i>Nesticella benoiti</i> (Hubert, 1970)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Helafricanus hastatus</i> (Wesotowska, 1986)	1	LC	STHE
FAMILY OECOBIIDAE				<i>Helafricanus insperatus</i> (Wesotowska, 1986)	1	LC	AE
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C	<i>Helafricanus nanus</i> (Wesotowska, 2003)	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY OONOPIDAE				<i>Helafricanus pistaciae</i> (Wesotowska, 2003)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Gamasomorpha humicola</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE	<i>Helafricanus proszynskii</i> (Wesotowska, 2003)	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY OXYOPIIDAE				<i>Helafricanus trepidus</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE	<i>Holcolaetis zuluensis</i> Lawrence, 1937	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Hyllus argyrotroxus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes hoggii</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesotowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE	<i>Menemerus bifurcus</i> Wesotowska, 1999	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes pallidecoloratus</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE	<i>Mogrus mathisi</i> (Berland & Millot, 1941)	0	LC	C
<i>Oxyopes vogelsangeri</i> Lessert, 1946	1	LC	AE	<i>Myrmarachne inflatipalpis</i> Wanless, 1978	1	LC	AE
<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE	<i>Myrmarachne marshalli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Peucetia viridis</i> (Blackwall, 1858)	1	LC	AE	<i>Myrmarachne solitaria</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE
FAMILY PALPIMANIDAE				<i>Myrmarachne uvira</i> Wanless, 1978	1	LC	AE
<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
FAMILY PHILODROMIDAE				<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesotowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE	<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesotowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE
<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE	<i>Pellenes modicus</i> Wesotowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	1	LC	AE
<i>Philodromus brachycephalus</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE	<i>Phlegra imperiosa</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	3	LC	SAE
<i>Thanatus dorsilineatus</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesotowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
<i>Tibellus gerhardi</i> Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994	1	LC	AE	<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE	<i>Planamarengo bimaculata</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	<i>Pseudicius gracilis</i> Haddad & Wesotowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
<i>Tibellus vossioni</i> Simon, 1884	1	LC	AE	<i>Rhene lingularis</i> Haddad & Wesotowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
FAMILY PHOLCIDAE				<i>Stenaelurillus guttiger</i> (Simon, 1901)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE				
FAMILY PHYXELIDIDAE							
<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE				

FAMILY/ SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	FAMILY/ SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
<i>Thyene bilineata</i> Lawrence, 1927	2	LC	STHE	FAMILY THOMISIDAE			
<i>Thyene bucculenta</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ansiea tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene muticus</i> (Simon, 1902)	1	LC	AE	<i>Camaricus nigrotesselatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	<i>Heriaeus peterwebbi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	2	LC	STHE
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	<i>Hewittia gracilis</i> Lessert, 1928	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyenula natalica</i> (Simon, 1902)	3	LC	SAE	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE	<i>Monaeses gibbus</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1984	3	LC	SAE
FAMILY SCYTODIDAE				<i>Monaeses quadrituberculatus</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
<i>Scytodes caffra</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
FAMILY SEGESTRIIDAE				<i>Parabomis elsae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020 *	3	LC	SAE
<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE	<i>Parabomis martini</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
FAMILY SELENOPIIDAE				<i>Parasmodix quadrituberculata</i> Jézéquel, 1966	1	LC	AE
<i>Anypops tuckeri</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE	<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Selenops kruegeri</i> Lawrence, 1940	1	LC	AE	<i>Runcinia depressa</i> Simon, 1906	1	LC	AE
<i>Selenops radiatus</i> Latreille, 1819	0	LC	C	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
FAMILY SPARASSIDAE				<i>Runcinia insecta</i> (L. Koch, 1875)	0	LC	C
<i>Eusparassus jaegeri</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE	<i>Runcinia tropica</i> Simon, 1907	1	LC	AE
<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	1	LC	AE	<i>Stiphropus affinis</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pseudomicrommata longipes</i> (Bösenberg & Lenz, 1895)	1	LC	AE	<i>Stiphropus intermedius</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
FAMILY STASIMOPIDAE				<i>Synema diana</i> (Audouin, 1826)	1	LC	AE
<i>Stasimopus hewitti</i> Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012*	5	VU	SAE	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Stasimopus oculatus</i> Pocock, 1897	3	LC	SAE	<i>Synema simoneae</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Stasimopus robertsi</i> Hewitt, 1910	5	LC	SAE	<i>Thomisops pupa</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
FAMILY TETRAGNATHIDAE				<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE
<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864)	0	LC	C	<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C	<i>Thomisus congoensis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE
<i>Tetragnatha demissa</i> L. Koch, 1872	0	LC	C	<i>Thomisus dalmasi</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Tetragnatha isidis</i> (Simon, 1880)	0	LC	C	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C
<i>Tetragnatha nitens</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C	<i>Thomisus granulatus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
<i>Tetragnatha subsquamata</i> Okuma, 1985	1	LC	AE	<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE
FAMILY THERAPHOSIDAE				<i>Thomisus machadoi</i> Comellini, 1959	1	LC	AE
<i>Augacephalus junodi</i> (Simon, 1904)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Brachionopus pretoriae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	DDT	SAE	<i>Thomisus spiculosus</i> Pocock, 1901	1	LC	AE
<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
FAMILY THERIDIIDAE				<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Anelosimus nelsoni</i> Agnarsson, 2006	3	LC	SAE	<i>Xysticus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
<i>Argyrodes argyrodes</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	0	LC	C	FAMILY TRACHELIDAE			
<i>Enoplognatha inornata</i> O.Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	<i>Afroceto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE	<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897	1	LC	AE
<i>Euryopis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C	<i>Thysanina serica</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C	FAMILY ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE	<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.Pickard-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE
<i>Latrodectus rhodesiensis</i> Mackay, 1973	2	LC	STHE	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
<i>Phoroncidia eburnea</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE				
<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C				
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C				
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE				